

Schiff's Base as a Colorimetric Reagent :
Pt. III. Spectrophotometric Studies of Iron (III) with the Schiff's
Base derived from β -Naphthyl Glyoxal and *p*-Dimethyl
Amino Aniline

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The formation of bluish green colour produced by the interaction of *p*-dimethyl amino anil of β -naphthyl glyoxal and Fe (III) has been studied to determine the composition, stability and other characteristics of the chelate formed. The absorbance curves of the complex show maxima at 600 m μ . The composition of the chelate has been established by three different methods, Job, slope and molar ratio. The chelate has a composition of 1:2. The stability constant of the chelate has been calculated by molar ratio method and comes out to 1.2×10^{12} . The value of RT log K at 25° is -16.61 K cal/mole.

A comprehensive programme of work has been undertaken in these laboratories on the preparation and properties of Schiff's base from phenyl glyoxal¹, β -naphthyl glyoxal² and aromatic amines. Saxena and Malik^{3,4} reported the formation of Hg (II) chelate with *p*-dimethyl amino anil of β -naphthyl glyoxal. In continuation of the same work it was thought of interest to study the chelate formation of Fe(III) with *p*-dimethyl amino anil of β -naphthyl glyoxal. The present communication deals with the above mentioned chelate along with the composition, nature and stability of the chelate.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Weighed quantities of ferric chloride (Johnson, Matthey & Co. Ltd.) were dissolved in acidulated distilled dry acetone, estimated by the usual methods and the solutions suitably diluted as necessary. The ligand was prepared by the method of Saxena and Malik² (loc. cit.). Its purity was determined by nitrogen estimation (calcd. for C₂₀H₁₈N₂O, N-9.27%; found 9.21%). Stock solution of the Schiff's base was prepared by direct weighing of the Schiff's base in dry acetone and the solutions of the required concentrations were obtained by dilution.

Apparatus:—Spectronic '20' Bausch and Lomb Spectrophotometer was employed for the measurement of absorbance. All measurements of absorbance were noted

1. Malik et al, *J. Chem. Engg. Date.*, 1966, 11, 210.
2. R. C. Saxena and W. U. Malik, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 307.
3. R. C. Saxena and W. U. Malik, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.* (in press)
4. R. C. Saxena and W. U. Malik, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.* (in press)

against dry distilled acetone blanks. The infra red spectra were recorded in a potassium bromide medium by Perkin Elmer Infra cord.

All the experiments were carried out in an air conditioned room maintained at $25 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Nature of the complex formed:—The method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁵ was employed to determine the nature of the complexes formed in solution. Mixtures containing 0 : 1; 2 : 1; 1 : 1, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 ratios of metal to ligand were prepared, keeping the total volume 25 ml. in each case. Absorbance measurements were carried out in the range of 325 m μ to 625 m μ . The observations show that only one complex is formed, having λ max. at 600 m μ . The λ max. of the reagent is at 435 m μ .

Mixtures containing 2×10^{-4} M of metals and 2.0×10^{-4} M reagent, retained the colour intensity even after 12 hours of standing at room temperature.

To estimate the empirical formula of the complex species, (i) the method of continued variations⁶, (ii) the mole ratio method⁷ and (iii) the slope ratio method⁷ were employed. The composition of the chelate has been found to be 1:2 by all the methods.

Evaluation of stability constant:—It was determined by mole ratio method⁷ from the equation

$$K = \frac{(m - \alpha c)(n - \alpha c)}{c(1 - \alpha)} \quad \text{with } \alpha = \frac{E_m - E_s}{E_m}$$

$$E_m = 0.90; \quad \alpha = 0.05 \text{ and } c = 0.125 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$$

$$E_s = 0.85$$

The value of K is 1.2×10^{12} . The free energy change of formation has also been calculated with the help of the expression $\Delta G^{\circ} = -RT \ln K$ and comes out to be -16.61 K cal/mole at 25° .

Isolation of the complex:—10 ml. of 0.005 M acetic solution of ferric chloride was taken in a beaker and nearly 25 cc of 0.005 M reagent solution was added to it. The resulting mixture was concentrated in a vacuum desiccator over calcium chloride when the bluish green crystals of the chelate were isolated. These crystals were washed several times with acetonitrile in order to wash out the adhering impurities of ferric chloride and the reagent and then dried in a vacuum desiccator.

Iron was estimated by the usual method. The total (ionisable and nonionisable) chlorine was estimated by Stepanow method⁸.

5. Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437; 1942, 64, 1630.

6. P. Job, *Ann. Chem.*, 1928, x, 9, 113.

7. Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.

8. H. Middleton, "Systematic qualitative organic analysis. Edward Arnold Ltd. 1962.

The results of analysis are as follows :-

Decomposition point. — 200°

Calculated%	Found%
Fe — 7.28; Cl — 13.90	Fe — 7.08; Cl — 13.12
C — 62.73; H — 4.66; and	C — 62.36; H — 4.61; and
N — 7.30	N — 6.96

I R. Studies: —The sites of interaction are keto and azomethine groupings. It appears that a resonance is experienced by the ligand under the influence of ferric chloride which makes the $>C=O$ more electron dense to facilitate the binding. In this complex there is a lowering of frequencies from those of $>C=O$ and $-CH=N$ groupings ($1700-1670\text{ cm}^{-1}$; $1600-1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$) respectively. This can only be possible when interaction at the two positions, $>C=O$ and $-CH=N$ grouping, takes place.

The ionic chlorine (calcd. 4.63%; found 3.86%) outside the coordination sphere of the chelate was estimated by titrating an ethanolic solution of the isolated complex with ethanolic silver nitrate⁹.

On the basis of the above facts the following structure is assigned.

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9. F. P. Treadwell and William T. Hall, "Analytical Chemistry," Vol. II. p. 292 quantitative. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. New York and London.